

Wf4Ever: Advanced Workflow Preservation Technologies for Enhanced Science

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D6.1: Genomics Workflow Preservation Requirements

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This deliverable provides initial requirements for Genomics Workflow Preservation

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Executive Summary

One of the main challenges for biomedical research lies in the integrative study of large and increasingly complex combinations of data in order to understand the mechanisms that explain the onset and progression of human diseases. Computer-assisted methodology is needed to perform increasingly complex integrative analysis, while upholding scientific principles such as reproducibility and the preservation of experimental materials and methods as evidence for our findings. Therefore we develop the concept of a Research Object in this project. From a biological perspective this is a structured container for the materials and methods involved in a computational experiment. They collect and organize the diversity of information needed to support a research finding, and can be exposed to colleagues and peers similar to sharing a notebook or a published methods section. At this time, there is no widely adopted standard for recording and publishing a computational experiment as part of a biological study. Several public resources offer partial solutions, such as the Human Genome project and its many followers. As part of their infrastructure to share data, they provide reliable references to their content and sometimes enforce formatting rules upon submission of data and metadata. Ontologies and Semantic Web tools provide additional means for referencing computational artefacts that will help useful archiving. For methods and code, myExperiment and BioCatalogue are obvious candidates to provide archiving facilities. Case studies at the Human Genetics Department of the Leiden University Medical Centre provide feedback and requirements for Wf4Ever developments, in particular a genotype-phenotype study for unravelling Metabolic Syndrome, and a study to reveal the role of epigenetics in Huntington's Disease. These provide real-life examples of what a Research Object may contain and mock-up interfaces structured underneath by the envisioned Research Object model. We defined a step-wise requirement analysis procedure between biologists and technologists via Wf4Ever intermediates. Requirements are extracted from non-technically focussed user scenarios, which in turn are prioritised through feedback from the biologists. We identified three user roles: (i) 'researcher user of workflows', (ii) comparator, (iii) reviewer. Our initial requirements are based on the first. The top ranked user requirements are (1) being able to reuse (parts of) workflows, (2) finding workflows on the web by their content, biological purpose, and outcome, (3) recording notes while designing or running workflows, (4) keeping everything together, and (5) facilitating the publication of research objects. We suggest two main types of research objects: 'Live' Research Objects, for recording and organizing material before publication, and the abridged and clarified copies ready for publication: Publication Research Objects.

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1. Genomics Workflow Preservation Requirements

1.1 Motivation and aims

One of the main challenges for biomedical research lies in the study of large and increasingly complex combinations of data in order to understand the mechanisms that explain the onset and progression of human diseases. Even if the genetic cause of a disease is clear, such as in the case of Huntington's Disease, we are still far from understanding the downstream processes that govern its progression. In the case of Metabolic Syndrome, even the genetic background for the predisposition to develop conditions such as diabetes or cardiovascular disease is still unclear. The general problem is that for all but the simplest biological systems, we do not have sufficient information to satisfactorily describe the system. Therefore, more and more data and more and more types of data are produced by the field. A combination of hypothesis driven and hypothesis free research is subsequently expected to promote (i) novel insights into the molecular mechanisms of a complex disease, (ii) biomarkers for earlier diagnosis, (iii) biological targets for treatment. In any case, new computer-assisted methodology is needed to perform increasingly complex integrative analysis while upholding the ability to reproduce and preserve the evidence for the biological conclusions we draw. To this end, we develop the concept of a 'Research Object' in this project. From the point of view of traditional experimental biology, a Research Object provides a digital analogue of the 'Materials and Methods' section of a research paper and the annotated protocols found in laboratory journals. Their purpose is to allow peers and colleagues to understand how the results of an experiment were obtained and to be able to reproduce them. Literature and notebooks have proven to be reliable means for archiving experimental protocols and associated information. Our wish is that Research Objects will provide a similar 'point of reference' for computational experiments, a container for the computational artefacts involved in an experiment. The Research Object Model provides structure, similar to the guidelines that journals impose on their Materials and Methods section.

An interesting aspect of digital preservation is the prospect of novel ways to perform post-hoc analysis. In this project we deploy semantic mining services that help interpret complex and noisy data, or predict novel biological relations by connecting experimental data to biological concepts [1]. We anticipate that by connecting semantically annotated results to the wf4ever preservation models we enable a new form of post-hoc analysis. Summarizing, the challenge in biomedicine is not just the volumes of data that we need to process, but the increasing complexity of the experiments that we wish to perform across many types of data. This has important consequences for the assurance of scientific quality of computational analysis, and thereby for the way we preserve computational experiments, their inputs and outputs, and their biological context.

1.2 State of the art

Currently, preservation of computational experiments is in its infancy in the biomedical domain. The traditions from wet laboratory biology provide a useful analogy, but do not provide sufficient mechanisms for archiving digital artefacts. Wet laboratory tradition prescribes the recording of the steps of an experiment in a laboratory log, later-on published as the 'materials and methods' section of a journal publication or in a book

of protocols. This allows peers, one's colleagues to start with, to evaluate and reuse the work for their own purposes. There is no widely adopted standard for recording and publishing a computational experiment as part of a biological study. Computational components, datasets, tools, etc., are sometimes submitted as 'supplemental information', which is typically relatively unstructured. Consequently, computational experiments are probably less rigorously evaluated than wet laboratory protocols, and reuse by peers may prove difficult.

A number of initiatives address certain aspects of preserving computational experiments. Biology has always been very data-oriented. Therefore, many projects address the need to share data among biologists, of which the Human Genome project is a famous starting point [2]. A vast number of public repositories of biological data now exist. Some of these, such as ArrayExpress¹ and the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO²) for gene expression, require specific metadata to be uploaded with the data, while in turn journals require researchers to submit this type of data into one of these repositories. In addition, numerous ontologies exist by which data in many public databases are annotated [3],[4]. This increases our ability to align data that pertain to the same ontological concept, and it has led to new types of analysis where data is analysed at the level of their ontological labels. Semantic Web languages and tools, based on W3C recommendations such as OWL and RDF³, further provide a framework to capture, expose, and query ontology-based metadata across multiple resources [5],[6]. The Linked Data principle has increased the popularity of making data sets interoperable on the web [7], including life science data [8]. The Concept Wiki is a recent initiative that aims to provide a community-curated resource of disambiguated concepts to the Semantic Web [9].

For methods and code, there are also initiatives that allow some form of archiving and sharing. These repositories usually address the need of users who are using a certain tool within a certain niche. For instance, the most popular way to do statistics in bioinformatics is by using the statistical programming language R and the tooling around it. BioConductor is a repository for sharing R packages that is highly popular among bioinformaticians⁴. Also in Wf4Ever we will make use of R when performing biostatistical analysis. Moving beyond the single niche, the BioCatalogue is a repository for sharing and annotating Web Services⁵ [10]. Currently, SOAP, REST and SOAPlab are supported. We hope BioCatalogue will further develop into a central point of reference for services and tools that run either locally or remotely.

Probably the most appropriate paradigm for capturing and archiving computational experiments is that of a workflow [11]. It allows focus on the steps of an experiment, hiding details of any particular programming language. This allows an archived experiment to be investigated beyond a single niche. A workflow is reminiscent of the protocol of a wet laboratory experiment, usually described in the 'Materials and Methods' section of a paper. MyExperiment seems the most obvious candidate to become the commonly used repository for sharing workflows⁶ [12]. It allows several types of workflows to be shared. Perhaps unfortunately, a common 'standard' workflow language has not emerged over the years, but this may be

¹ <http://www.ebi.ac.uk/arrayexpress/>

² <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/>

³ Web Ontology Language, <http://www.w3.org/2004/OWL/>; Resource Description Framework, <http://www.w3.org/RDF/>

⁴ <http://www.bioconductor.org/>

⁵ <http://www.biocatalogue.org/>

⁶ <http://www.myexperiment.org/>

partly overcome by using common ontologies and Semantic Web formats to capture the metadata and provenance of workflows (metadata at design time and run time). An important aspect of both BioCatalogue and myExperiment is their explicit aim to provide persistent unique references (web-based URLs) for their content, analogue to journal papers providing references for their content.

Finally, Wf4Ever is among a number of recent initiatives that aim to apply Semantic Web principles to make scientific information interoperable, and align certain types of data. Minimal information models, such as MIAME for gene expression data, help to 'harmonize' data, while Semantic Web languages and tools allow meaningful integration across the web[13],[14]. 'Nano-publications' could provide a basic mechanism by which to expose biological relations, observed or hypothesized, and their provenance [15],[16]. The object, predicate, and subject for these relations are envisioned to refer to the Concept Wiki or otherwise commonly accepted naming schemes and ontologies compliant with the Semantic Web. In our project, we aspire to provide a minimal semantic model for structuring and exposing Research Objects. As users, we rely on recommended models such that we know what to expect from Research Object compliant resources. At the same time, the Semantic Web approach allows us to map to personal models and link to our own resources. An obvious link to make is between nano-publications and Research Objects when novel biological relations were the result of a computational experiment.

1.3 Use cases

The department of human genetics of the Leiden University Medical Centre investigates the genetic background and molecular mechanisms behind a substantial number of rare and common diseases. An important technological focus is on high throughput genome sequencing to study genome wide genetic variation (e.g. across all ~22000 genes). Various other types of data are collected in order to unravel the molecular basis for the progression of diseases and for finding new leads for treatment. Each of the studies can provide requirements for Wf4Ever, because for all of them the management and maintenance of the computational components, data and methods, before and after publication is a challenge. Here, we focus on three examples. The first is the primary case study dedicated to Wf4Ever.

1.3.1 Metabolic Syndrome

Metabolic Syndrome is defined by a number of clinical criteria, such as waist circumference, blood pressure, and glucose levels. When these criteria are met, the risk of developing for instance diabetes type II and cardiovascular disease are increased. The syndrome is not defined by underlying biological phenomena. In fact, the biological cause of the development of its associated diseases is unclear. In an ageing and increasingly obese population this is unsatisfactory. Given the many questions regarding this syndrome, we will conduct studies to mine for relations in data ranging from the genotype (genetic code) to the phenotype (disease symptoms). These include Genome Wide Association studies (GWAS) by which the genetic variation in all genes of a large number of individuals are statistically analysed in relation to traits such as having a certain disease or not. When specimen of individuals are also collected for research we speak of a biobank. The Erasmus Rucphen Family (ERF) study is an example [17]. Rucphen is a small town in the Netherlands of which the population was asked to provide information via surveys and through a number of biomedical measurements, such as an MRI scan by which metabolites can be measured in specific parts of the body. Family relations in the community help establish the heritability of the

syndrome. The wide range of measurements should allow new hypotheses to be formed about the disease.

In terms of Wf4Ever requirements, the complexity of the analyses of such a range of measurements will require a sophisticated mechanism for capturing and referencing the data that was used in an experiment, its outcome, and the biological interpretation. Flexibility and perhaps pragmatism is needed, because not all data will have the same access rights or can be stored in one place. Each type of measurement may come with its own specific means of data handling and analysis. Taking this into account, being able to evaluate an archived experiment may be a more realistic goal than being able to rerun it effortlessly.

1.3.2 The role of epiGenetics in Huntington's Disease

The genetic mutation that causes Huntington's disease (HD) was identified 20 years ago but the downstream molecular mechanisms leading to the HD phenotype are still poorly understood. Epigenetic phenomena such as DNA methylation and histone modifications can cause long-term changes in gene expression over generations of dividing cells [18]. Effects at the level of DNA and higher orders of DNA organisation have been shown to play an important role in the HD pathogenesis [19],[20]. It is clear that new hypotheses that take into account epigenetic mechanisms may shed some light on the downstream mechanisms that lead to HD symptoms. We started a project to test and augment such hypotheses. Here, we use workflow systems and semantic web techniques to integrate several bioinformatics methodologies, such as microarray data analysis and text mining, while digitally archiving the computational procedures and their results for post-analysis.

In preparation of our first analysis we have made an inventory of components (Table 1). These help identify what a Research Object may contain. Our first plan is to analyse micro-array gene expression profiles from HD samples and correlate these with specific regions of the genome that are known to be markers for epigenetic mechanisms (e.g. CpG islands have an altered methylation state in active genes). In addition, we will link the dataset to biological concepts by mining biomedical literature [21]. This allows us to statistically analyse the data together with their previously asserted biological meaning [22]. We plan to structure the results of the workflow using Semantic Web models of [23], using the emerging Research Object model as a template to link the elements in Table 1. Combining knowledge and data in a highly structured way may gain us new insight into the role of epigenetic mechanisms in HD disease aetiology, while the trail to evidence is preserved.

Apart from a convenient container for (references) to the components of our experiments, we will require mechanisms to annotate experimental results with semantic models, including models provided by Wf4Ever. As such, results over several experiments become semantically linked, both through biological semantics, as well as procedural semantics provided by the Research Object model. We anticipate that for users the annotation tooling could be made to have the same role as the notebook in the wet laboratory.

Object	Description	Type	Version *	Role in the experiment
1. DATASETS				
HD dataset 1	Human brain dataset. 44 HD samples, 36 Controls age and sex matched. Brain areas: caudate nucleus, frontal cortex and cerebellum. Affymetrix platform. Rows correspond to probe ids and columns to samples.	GEO series datafile		To be used as input into the workflow model and be analysed
HD dataset 2	Mouse model dataset. Controls and HDACi 4b treated samples from WT and R6/2 transgenic mice. Brain regions: cortex, cerebellum, striatum. Illumina platform. Rows correspond to probe ids and columns to samples.	GEO series datafile		To be used as input into the workflow and be analysed
2. SCRIPTS				
Analyse data	Script for the process and analysis of the datasets. Input: data matrix, tab delimited. Rows → genes, columns → samples Output: list of differentially expressed genes R packages needed: Bioconductor, Affy, Limma, GEOquery	R script	R version 2.10.1	Normalize data ; identification of differentially expressed genes
GO/KEGG enrichment	Script for GO enrichment analysis. Input: List of genes Output: A data matrix in which the rows correspond to genes, and for each gene a GO annotation is assigned together with a p-value. Rows are not unique (a gene can be annotated with more than one processes/function) R packages needed: Global Test	R script	R version 2.10.1	Annotate genes with biological terms (molecular functions, biological processes, cellular component). For each relation gene – annotation a p-value is assigned, representing the significance of each term.
3. WEB SERVICES				
CpG island enrichment	Webservice performing CpG enrichment to a list of genes. If the list is in FASTA format performs directly the enrichment or else calls another service GET_FASTA and transforms our list to FASTA format and then does the CpG island enrichment	Web service		CpG island enrichment
4. WORKFLOWS				
SigWin detector v2	Workflow which maps genes to their chromosomal location and identifies RIDGES and Anti-RIDGES	Taverna workflow	Taverna version 2	Map genes to chromosomal positions
5. DOCUMENTATION				
Hodges <i>et al.</i> 2006	Published paper for dataset1	PDF file		Reference paper for dataset 1
HDAC i4b	Published paper for dataset2	PDF file		Reference paper for dataset 2
SigWin detector	Paper about the workflow used in the analysis for the genome mapping	PDF file		Explanation about the SigWin-detector workflow model
Global test	Paper explaining the global test method which we used for our analysis	PDF file		Paper about the global test method for GO/KEGG annotation

Table 1: Preliminary inventory of Research Object components gathered during the design phase of the first experiment to study the role of epigenetics in Huntington's Disease. The content of a 'live' Research Object, i.e. this table, changes during experimentation. At the same time, user side prototypes of Research Object architecture are tested.

1.3.3 Toxicogenomics – experience from a novice user

In the first months of this project we asked student Dennis Leenheer, a novice to Taverna, to build a workflow from existing components. His role is therefore that of a 'researcher user of workflows'. His biological aim was to interpret the effect of a gene transcription factor, synthetic Peroxisome Proliferator Activated Receptor Alpha stimulator (fibrate WY14643), on the gene-expression in the small intestines from both wild type and PPARalpha-null mice [22]. His user story was used to extract requirements for Wf4Ever.

Dennis discovered several useful workflows on myExperiment.org, but reuse was hampered by broken workflows or because of poor annotation of all or parts of the workflow. It was difficult to find and extract the components that he needed. Apparently, users need ample persuasion to provide sufficient documentation or annotation for others to intelligently reuse a workflow. We also have our own statistical tests implemented in R scripts, and with our help Dennis built a workflow from R components. A straightforward conclusion is that reuse of workflow components is hard, requires user-oriented documentation, and often personal experience with the methods and tools. Interestingly, we observe that this situation is similar in wet laboratory practice: biologists preferably choose familiar protocols, because these give them a better chance of making them work. We concluded that to support reuse, we require notebook facilities that designers and users of workflows can use to describe what they do and why. We wish to be able to provide appropriate notes at the appropriate times. As a side effect, these tools would gather machine-readable information that allow us to build tooling on top of Research Objects. An example is tooling that helps find and understand workflows, without which archiving of workflows has little use for biologists.

1.4 Requirements

1.4.1 Requirement analysis

In this project we combine real-life biomedical case studies with technological research and development. Our aim for the use cases is not merely to demonstrate 'a use' of technology, but to investigate a number of real biological cases while using Wf4Ever (and associated) concepts and technologies. The current state of technologies allows us to take this approach, but we take into account that the time line of biological studies does not necessarily align with the dynamics of IT research and development. Therefore, Wf4Ever 'mediators', bioinformaticians committed to the Wf4Ever goals, play an important role. We gather user scenarios and user requirements from our own past experience, experience from our case studies, and by interviewing biology colleagues who do not have a technical background. The perspective at this stage is entirely that of the biologist. The results are available through the Wf4Ever wiki and are used to isolate the requirements that drive Wf4Ever research and development (see Figure 2 in D4.1). At these stages the perspective becomes that of the computer scientist, but the isolated requirements are reflected back to the biologists in a simplified form for review, prioritisation and to manage expectations for the biological applications. Table 2 summarizes such a simplified list. Where appropriate, we provide mock-ups of envisioned user interfaces that would meet a requirement (Figure 1). We let the analogy with

Figure 2 - Mock-up of a notebook component in Taverna. Notebook components could be implemented in various applications related to Research Objects. The Research Object Model would provide structure and ontology-based annotation facilities.

traditional preservation techniques in experimental biology play an important role such that first iterations will have a sense of familiarity. Although the first six months represent a milestone for requirements in the project, the feedback between the biological cases and the IT developments is continuous.

Use for experiments	Record	Search
reuse workflows/protocols, in part or whole, for my own work	record my initial experimental hypothesis (my goals)	on the web
suggest ideas and alternatives to my envisaged approach	record my revised experimental hypothesis	in my local organisation
compare executed workflows/protocols & their results with mine	record notes while designing and running my experiment	in my local research team
reference the work that provides the input for my analysis	record versions of parts that I take from elsewhere (e.g. remote tools or standard protocols)	by recorded methods
use my own scripts/local methods	make recorded information part of a publication	by recorded biological purpose
adapt an existing workflow/protocol to my needs	keep everything about my experiment together	by recorded input
execute an existing workflow/protocol with different data/samples	easily use recorded information for a publication (e.g. as supplemental information)	by recorded output
	store recorded information before publication as long as possible	
	store recorded information after publication as long as possible	

Table 2: Simplified list of requirements for digital 'Materials and Methods', aka Research Objects

1.4.2 User roles

In the first phase of the project we identified three main types of users. They have many similarities and are not mutually exclusive, but their main aim differs and they differ in quality requirements. We

requested to focus first on the first type of user as this will have the most immediate impact on researchers, and will naturally build towards the other user types.

Researcher User of Workflows (in short: (re)user): the scientist who is looking for workflows as a basis for answering her research question. This could be the person doing the experiment or her supervisor (usually together). The goal is to find a workflow that can form the basis of one's own.

Comparator: this is where a researcher compare her work, or her planned work, with the competition. This is typically done before a new experiment (overlapping with the activity of a reuser), but also at later stages (e.g. before publishing). The goal is to compare, not to use the workflows as the basis for one's own work.

Reviewer: this is when a researcher needs to evaluate the work of a peer. It has similarity with comparing. However, the goal is to evaluate the quality of the peer's work, not to relate this work directly to one's own.

1.4.3 Summary of user requirements

In D4.1 and elsewhere detailed lists of requirements can be found that were extracted from the user stories and scenarios from the biology and astronomy cases. Table 2 contains the list of requirements that we simplified to obtain new feedback from biology (and astronomy) users. We asked wet laboratory biologists to use the analogy with wet laboratory protocols. Their feedback confirmed the items on these list in general. Of particular interest are (1) being able to reuse (parts of) workflows, (2) finding workflows on the web by their content, biological purpose, and outcome, (3) recording notes while designing or running workflows, (4) keeping everything together, and (5) facilitating the publication of research objects.

For realistic use of Research Objects and workflows, support for potentially large datasets is a requirement. While designing and running in silico experiments before publication, data movement is often a bottleneck. This should be taken into account when developing prototypes for this stage of case study research. When a Research Object is published, a reference may be sufficient. This will allow another user to retrieve the required data, or at least recover the precise origin of the data. Unfortunately, we cannot expect a guarantee that in all cases referenced data exists persistently, unless we include hard copies in a Research Object.

1.5 In conclusion: Expectations from Research Objects

As users we expect the concept of a Research Object to provide at least two things: (i) a container for our computational materials and methods, including (references to) data, recorded notes, and biological knowledge (hypothesis, interpretation) (ii) a structured point of reference for what is recorded and subsequently published as a Research Object. We assume that the Research Object model exposes some recommended semantics and structure, providing a common reference for users and application builders. The structure alone is not sufficient; peers should have access to information that exposes what its content is about, such as the biological purpose, and the type of methods and results that it contains. As such, we think that the archive can become an active part of

the scientific process, similar to scientific publications. The main bottleneck here is obtaining the necessary metadata from researchers who create the Research Objects. We see two ways to address this: (i) make annotation a side-effect of a notebook service for creators, (ii) strive to give Research Objects the status of a publication. For the former, we wish to experiment with an interface that will provide a simple web form in appropriate places as a digital analogue for the laboratory notebook, i.e. when using Taverna, we might add notes about the parameters of a service for ourselves and our colleagues. When we publish a research object we may wish to emphasize the scientific context and provide notes for reviewers and peers. In turn, comments of reviewers would provide additional metadata about the use and quality of the Research Object. Next to technical solutions, we anticipate that a requirement by journal editors to provide a properly annotated workflow or Research Object is the ultimate incentive to overcome the annotation bottleneck.

We identified two types of research objects: (i) the 'live' or 'working object' that we use while experimenting, and (ii) the publication object, modelled after journal publications. The former are mutable and would be expected to be relatively 'dirty'. The latter are cleaned-up copies of working objects, ready for publication, hence evaluation by peers. Similar to paper publications, we would expect these to be immutable. Not all references will be under our control, and certainly not all data can be stored in a Research Object. However, we expect the research object and its content to have timestamps, so that at least we can see at what time the workflow in the Research Object was validated to produce the referenced results.

We further expect that the Research Object Model will link to other models via shared ontologies. In particular, we expect models for Scientific Discourse and nano-publications to provide a gateway to other knowledge bases relevant for biological research. This will allow us to explore new ways to study knowledge across many experiments.

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